

Detection of Volatile Compounds of Biological Interest as Cancer Biomarkers in Saliva Using Controlled-Atmosphere Flexible Micro Tube Plasma Ionization (CA-FuTP) and Mass Spectrometry

Pascal Vogel¹, Constantinos Lazarou², Odhisea Gazeli², Sebastian Brandt¹, Joachim Franzke¹, David Moreno- González^{1,3}

¹Leibniz-Institut für analytische Wissenschaften, Bunsen-Kirchhoff-Str. 11, 44139 Dortmund, Germany

²ENAL Electromagnetics and Novel Applications Lab, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus

³Analytical Chemistry Research Group, Department of Physical and Analytical Chemistry, University of Jaén, 23071 Jaén, Spain

E-mail: dmgonzal@ujaen.es

Within the last decade, atmospheric pressure plasmas have been widely investigated for their application as soft ionization sources for mass spectrometry (MS) [1]. The flexible micro tube plasma (F μ TP) emerged as a desirable ionization source due to its small size, safety and low helium consumption [2]. Replacing the ambient atmosphere with controlled atmosphere (CA) allows for a significant improvement in the limit of the detection (LOD) of the analyte [3]. Putting it all together as shown in Fig. 1, an F μ TP under CA was used for the detection of volatile organic cancer biomarkers in saliva matrix. For the CA, ambient air, synthetic air (80% N₂ and 20% O₂) and synthetic air with Argon were investigated. The optimum LOD was obtained for synthetic air found for. The results for 13 different biomarkers showed the LOD improved by an average factor of 2.5 compared to the state of art [4].

Fig. 1: The analyte is introduced through gas chromatography (GC) and is ionized by the F μ TP.

This project has received funding from EUs H2020 research and innovation programme under agreement NO. 810686

References

- [1]F. Andrade et al, Anal Chem 2008, 80 (8), 2654-63.
- [2]S. Brandt, et al., Anal Chem 2018, 90 (17), 10111-10116.
- [3]P. Vogel, et al., Anal Chem 2019, 91 (5), 3733-3739.
- [4]P. Vogel, et al., Anal Chem 2020, 92 (14), 9722-9729.